

Martin Heidegger on the Notion of “Dwelling”: Implications for Environmental Sustainability

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Abstract

This paper examines Martin Heidegger’s notion of *dwelling* and its implications for environmental sustainability. The central thrust of this work is Heidegger’s interpretation of *dwelling* and its relevance to his understanding of our interconnectedness with nature. For Heidegger, the human-nature relationship is ontological and he demonstrates this view through his conception of care and the fourfold. Through care we establish our authentic relationship to the natural world, and through the fourfold we assert our ontological relation to the world. This position by Heidegger paves the way for environmental concerns as mortals that inhabit the Earth. As mortals who dwell, for Heidegger, *dwelling* ontologically inseparable from our responsibility to nature. We are not merely occupying space and time but we are fundamental parts of a holistic system of being. Therefore, environmental sustainability is an inevitable and integral part of our responsibility as dwellers on the Earth and this goes beyond our immediate space and time. This perspective by Heidegger sets the stage for a critical approach to the sustainability debate based on his ontological insights. This insight is necessary for addressing the issue of environmental sustainability by adopting a mindful and intentional approach that is rooted in moral responsibility.

Keywords: Martin Heidegger, Dwelling, Environmental Sustainability, Care,

Introduction

Martin Heidegger's notion of *dwelling* offers insights into the nature-human relationship and its implications for environmental sustainability. Heidegger believed that *dwelling* goes beyond mere physical occupation of a building; it involves a deep sense of belonging and connection to the natural world. By understanding and embracing this perspective, we can begin to reevaluate our relationship with the environment and strive towards sustainable practices that prioritise environmental harmony and stewardship.

Martin Heidegger is not an outright environmental philosopher, but his contribution to the philosophical enterprise encapsulates a system of thought that embraces what he considers the essence of reality or being. A common theme in Heidegger's works is his analysis of words and language, which he believes reveals the hidden meaning and truth behind our existence. This familiar theme is seen in his analysis of terms like *Alethia*, *techne*, *Dasein*, *dwelling*, and things, among others. Therefore, the interrelationship between the essence of being and language is established when he infers that language is the house of being (Zaner and Ihde 1973). Therefore, language plays a crucial role in shaping our understanding of being and existence.

Understanding this approach by Heidegger is pertinent to the exploration of the notion of *dwelling* and its significance for environmental sustainability. The significance is evident in Heidegger's depiction of the natural world as an ontological edifice where being is. Hence, our relationship with this edifice is purely ontological. This implies that our relationship with being is established by our presence at the nexus of being through space and time. This presence of man is in tandem with the presence of being because it represents our place in reality, or the scheme of things (Heidegger 2001).

In relation to Heidegger's notion of being, environmental sustainability entails an ontological responsibility to the natural world and others. This ontological responsibility requires us to recognise the interconnectedness of all beings and their intrinsic value. Heidegger's position is that we should "let being be seen in

their unconcealment"(Heidegger 2010). Letting being be suggests that we should not impose our will or exploit the natural world but to live in harmony with it. This means taking into consideration the long-term consequences of our actions on the environment and other beings. Heidegger's philosophy calls for a shift in our mindset and behaviour towards a more sustainable and respectful relationship with the natural world. Therefore, achieving environmental sustainability involves making choices that prioritise the well-being of both present and future generations, as well as the preservation of the value inherent in nature.

Environmental Sustainability

A definition of environmental sustainability first requires a definition of sustainability to understand its meaning when applied to the environment. The word sustainability was first used by a German forester, Hans Carl von Carlowitz, in his 1712 work titled *Sylvaicultura Oeconomica*. This term was used to propose how forests should be managed over the long term. The term became widely used in the 1980s as an offshoot of the environmental movement that began in the 1960s and 1970s (Scoones 2007). It describes how growth and development could be applied to environmental issues. The commission, led by former Norwegian Prime Minister Gro Brundtland, championed the discussion of sustainability, which was the subject of a 1987 report titled *Our Common Future*. The report defined sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED 1987a: 43). This definition implies that human beings implicitly have a responsibility for the well-being of future generations.

Scoones defines sustainability as "the ability of a system to bounce back from such shocks and stresses and adopt stable states" (Scoones 2007). This definition is in response to the concerns of ecologists about "how ecosystems respond to shocks and stress" (Scoones 2007). These shocks and stresses represent activities that affect the balance of the ecosystem and may cause adverse ripple effects. The terms sustainability and sustainable development have generated a lot of debate, especially about their definition. However, for Morelli, the term sustainability is useless without a modifier like ecological, agricultural, or economic (Morelli 2011). This idea has inspired the use of the term with modifiers like social and

"environmental," which all connect to the environment. This has led to the postulation by Goodland that there is an intrinsic relationship between social, economic, and environmental responsibility (Goodland 1995). This is evident in the fact that the social, economic, and environmental sectors all try to address the same issue from different perspectives. This is aside from the fact that the key decision-makers when it comes to environmental sustainability are human beings. Morelli goes further to define "environmental sustainability as the maintenance of natural capital" (Morelli 2011). This natural capital is the equivalent of our natural environment, which includes biotic and abiotic components. Nature is in a constant cycle of production if unchecked by the activities of humans. However, when these activities exceed the production of natural capital, future generations may suffer. Addressing these challenges will require a comprehensive approach that takes into account the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of the problem.

However, from its origin, the term sustainability entails the management of natural resources over the long term. From its origin, there was no explicit implication of human responsibility for the environment. However, by considering the management of natural resources for the longest possible period, the notion of duty becomes implicit. This means that humans must ensure nature and its resources lasts for the longest possible time. It means living with nature in such a way that its longevity is not threatened. This sudden threat to nature is the purpose of the sustainability debate. The sustainability debate aims to address the urgent need for humans to find ways to coexist with nature without causing harm or depletion. It highlights the importance of finding innovative solutions and adopting practices that promote environmental preservation and conservation. This notion of coexistence with nature is what Heidegger tries to address in his notion of *dwelling*.

Heidegger on the notion of "Dwelling"

In the section titled "Building Dwelling Thinking" in his work *Poetry, Language, Thought*, Heidegger tries to answer two questions. The first question is what *dwelling* entails, and the second is how the notion of building relates to *dwelling*. He asserts that we attain *dwelling* through building, but not every edifice is a *dwelling* in the ontological sense. For example, train stations, roads, dams, and

marketplaces are all built, but they are not *dwelling*s, even though they are encapsulated in the greater notion of *dwelling*. Heidegger aims to delve into the true meaning of *dwelling* and building from its origin to elucidate its ontological relevance to our existential experience. He opines that the true meaning of the word building, from its Old English and High German origins (*buan*), has been lost. Heidegger believes that the true meaning of the term *buan* has been obscured over time, and he seeks to uncover its original significance. He argues that understanding the ontological connection between *dwelling* and building is crucial for comprehending our existence in the world. He affirms that *dwelling* is a fundamental part of our nature as mortals on earth (Heidegger 2001).

Heidegger infers that to dwell means "to cherish and protect, to preserve and care for, specifically to till the soil, to cultivate the vine" (Heidegger 2001). He, however, acknowledges the distinction between building as cultivating and building as constructing. Building as cultivating entails stewardship towards nature, while building as constructing entails things like building ships or temples. However, the two modes of building are subsumed in the greater notion of building. Heidegger concludes by affirming that building is indeed *dwelling* and both terms are ontologically inseparable. Dwelling for him is the way mortals inhabit the earth. Building as *dwelling* manifests through cultivation and construction. Cultivation involves the growing of things, and construction involves the erection of edifices (Heidegger 2001).

Building in the form of cultivation involves the careful nurturing and development of the natural environment, ensuring its sustainability with human existence. On the other hand, building as constructing encompasses the physical creation of structures that serve various purposes, shaping the human-made landscape. Both cultivation and construction are essential aspects of building, reflecting our desire to shape and experience the world. Cultivation focuses on the growth of plants, crops, and ecosystems, fostering biodiversity and providing resources for sustenance. Meanwhile, construction involves the design and assembly of buildings, roads, bridges, and other infrastructure that support human activities.

Both constructing and cultivating are subsumed in the notion of building, which is in turn interwoven with *dwelling*. Heidegger affirms that building and *dwelling* are the same and that *dwelling* is the way mortals inhabit the earth. He further establishes that the fundamental feature of *dwelling* is manifested in the sparing and preservation of nature. He comes to this view by analysing the meaning of the Old Saxon word for building, *woun*, and the Old Gothic word *wunian*. Both words, when translated, mean "to be at peace, to be brought to peace, to remain in peace." However, peace in this context entails freedom from harm, danger, or any other threat. Hence, this freedom means to spare and preserve nature, allowing it to exist in its natural state without being harmed or threatened. Thus, he affirms that "the fundamental character of *dwelling* is this sparing and preserving" (Heidegger 2001). The notion of *dwelling* represents a primal oneness, which manifests itself in the form of mortals, divinities, earth, and sky. This primal oneness is characterised by a harmonious coexistence between mortals, divinities, the earth, and the sky. It emphasises the interconnectedness and interdependence of all beings within their natural environment. This primal oneness is what he calls the fourfold.

Heidegger on the Fourfold of Being

The fourfold is Heidegger's way of articulating the interconnectedness and interdependence of mortals, divinities, earth, and sky within the primal notion of *dwelling*. It highlights the essential unity and harmony that exists between these entities, emphasising the importance of preserving this balance to maintain freedom and allow nature to exist in its natural state. Heidegger believed that by recognising and respecting this fourfold, individuals can cultivate a deeper connection to nature and live more authentically. Through this understanding, he sought to inspire a greater appreciation for the interconnectedness of all beings and the environment.

Heidegger's concept of the fourfold is elucidated in his work *Poetry, Thought, Language* in the section titled "The Thing". In this section of the aforementioned work, Heidegger begins with an analysis of the gains of technology and its benefits. Heidegger highlights some of the benefits of technology like planes that now allow man to travel across continents faster; radio that allows the instant transmission of information; cameras that allow the capture of natural events on film and television that allow the transmission of said events. It would seem man

has shortened the longest distances and put everything within the shortest possible range of himself. However, for Heidegger, this presumed nearness or shortness of distance is an illusion. He asserts that what is far from us in proximity can be near to us and vice versa, hence this short distance is not nearness nor long distance remoteness. Nearness for Heidegger is not about geographic proximity or the abolition of distances (Heidegger, 2001). It is about our affinity with the essence of being and the world.

Heidegger opines that distance brings no nearness and nearness is not about the shortness of distance. Short distance or great distance is not equivalent to nearness or remoteness. This is evident according to his analysis that even with the abolition of great distances, everything is neither far nor near, everything is uniformly without distance. According to him, the explosion of the atomic bomb already occurred before the actual event took place because the anxiety of its potential impact already haunted us. These terrifying feats show that technological conquests do not guarantee nearness, hence, the nearness of things remains absent even with technological conquests. In essence, nearness cannot be encountered directly according to him, and we may attempt to reach it through what we consider near to us in proximity. These things that are near to us and within our reach are what Heidegger calls things (Heidegger, 2001).

In his analysis of what a thing is, Heidegger begins by using the illustration of a jug. A jug is a thing as a container made by a potter that holds something. The jug is not so because it was made but it was made as a container that holds something. Hence, the nature of the jug is not determined by its making but the jug had to prepare itself for the task of holding something. The jug manifests itself in the process of making by the potter, this manifestation is the idea of something made. By looking at the outward manifestation of the jug we encounter the idea of the jug which stands as a being manifesting as a container of some sort, herein lies the thingness of the jug. We only become aware of the jug as a thing or its nature when we fill the jug with some substance. The jug's outward parts show that it is tailored to be held, and even the external parts of the jug have some use. The jug as a thing is made up of various parts, but the thingness of the jug is in its ability to hold some substance (Heidegger, 2001).

However, Heidegger asks if the jug is empty, hence the thingness of the jug as a container lies in the void or space that it holds and not in the material that it is made of. He believes that we are misled when we consider the jug from the perspective of the void or emptiness as its defining attribute. A scientific study of the jug elucidates the fact that the jug was never empty, but when liquid is poured in, the liquid displaces the air that once filled it. Science is therefore guilty of not letting things be themselves as the standard for Being or reality. He goes further to use the explosion of the atomic bomb and its subsequent destruction as an example of the symbolism of the destruction of the thing itself. This implies that the thingness of the thing remains concealed. Therefore the nature of the thing in itself never becomes manifest because of the delusion of science as a superior tool for reaching reality and that scientific inquiry leaves the thing tainted, letting the thing be itself (Heidegger, 2001).

When Heidegger conceives of the destruction of the thing, he infers that the thingness of the thing is concealed and its true nature never comes to light. In explanation of the concept of nearness, Heidegger asserts that it concerns the neglect of the representation of the thing as a thing to himself. However, man can only ignore what is presented to him, hence, the need to understand the notion of nearness and its implications for man. The implications are demonstrated by his use of the Jug to understand the reality and effective features of the jug. For him, the distinctive feature of the jug is the ability to hold by keeping and retaining its contents. The ability of the jug to hold or retain its content is intertwined with its ability to give or pour out, there is no separating the two. He uses this description to explain the interconnectedness of Being through the outpouring of the jug. This outpouring is for him the fundamental feature of the jug as a jug, and in its essence, the sky and earth dwell (Heidegger, 2001).

The definition of the jug as a jug is demonstrated in two-folds according to Heidegger, the first is in its outpouring and the poured which describes its presence of giving and the empty jug also retains this nature. The content of the jug that gives is the water in which dwells the mingling of sky and earth. This pouring out Heidegger calls a gift, and it provides drinks for mortals when they are thirsty. But the same jug can also retain wine which is also given for consecration in the form of libation for the immortal gods which he considers the

authentic gift. By this giving of consecrated libation, the pouring jug manifests as the gift that gives. Thus in the gift of water and wine, both the sky and earth dwell. In the gift of outpouring the drink, mortals stay in their lane, and in the gift of outpouring that is libation, the divinities stay in their ways. For earth and sky, dwell in the gift of outpouring. Therefore in the gift of outpouring earth and sky, divinities and mortals dwell intertwined as one. This outpouring from the jug is a libation Heidegger calls "gush" (*guss* or *giessen* in German), a term which describes it as gift and sacrifice.

The fourfold (*das Geviert*) of Being is a way of thinking of things that manifests through the outpouring in the form of divinities, mortals, earth and sky. Each aspect of the fourfold dwells in their way individually but at the same time dwells together as one and according to Heidegger, "they are enfolded into a single fourfold" (Heidegger, 2001, p. 171). The outpouring is a gift because it manifests earth and sky, divinities and mortals. This manifestation is not merely persistence through space and time, it is the appropriation of the four-fold into a mutual Being. They are different in their singleness but at the same time intertwined into a single entity manifesting itself in four distinctive ways. They belong to one another and are betrothed or entrusted, they are unconcealed, hence the outpouring reveals the singleness of the fourfold of this mode of Being. All this is possible through the presencing or the persistence of the jug through space and time.

The fourfold is the coming together of divinities, mortals, earth and sky into the constitution or forming of things. In his description of the four items that constitute the fourfold, he defines mortals as "the humans. They are named the mortals because they can die ". For the earth, he considers " the building bearer, the nurturing fructifying, tending the waters and stones, what grows and the animals". The sky for Heidegger is "the journey of the sun, the course of the moon, the twinkle of the stars, the seasons of the year, light and twilight of the day, dark and light of the night, the favour and the inhospitality of the weather, the drawing of the clouds and the blue depths of the ether". The divinities ``are the hinting messengers of godhood", they divinities are not God or gods but those who are god-like and have become messengers by their closeness to the divine (Heidegger, 1976).

Heidegger's idea of the fourfold is deeply interwoven with his concept of things. Heidegger uses the term things to define objects that have a presence and significance beyond their mere utility or function. He believed that by acknowledging the inherent value of things, individuals could develop a more profound understanding of their place in the world and their relationship to the environment. The idea of the inherent value of entities in his analysis of things and their interconnectedness in nature gives us insight into his ethical consideration of the environment.

However, this idea of the interconnectedness of entities in nature is not peculiar only to the philosophy of Heidegger. For example, Arne Naess' deep ecology also emphasises the interconnectedness of all living beings and their environment, promoting a holistic approach to environmental ethics (Naess 2017). Similarly, Aldo Leopold also considers the interconnectedness of all living beings in his land ethic and calls for a moral responsibility towards the land and its inhabitants (Leopold 1970). Both Naess and Leopold's philosophies align with Heidegger's notion of *dwelling*, emphasising the importance of recognising and respecting the unity and harmony that exist within nature.

Heidegger on the notion of "Care"

Heidegger's analysis of care is found in chapter six of his seminal work, *Being and Time* (1927). In this chapter, Heidegger delves into the concept of care as a fundamental structure of human existence. He argues that care is not simply a feeling or emotion but rather a mode of being-in-the-world that encompasses our everyday activities and interactions. Through his analysis, Heidegger reveals how care shapes our understanding of ourselves, others, and the world around us, ultimately highlighting its crucial role in our existential experience.

Heidegger uses the term care (*sorge*) relative to *Dasein* as a "Being-in-the-world" to describe the relationship between human beings and Being. The notion of *Dasein*'s looking out into the world is manifested in care, according to Heidegger. Care is an ontological structural concept that shows the relationship between Being and *Dasein* and is evidence of the Being of *Dasein*. But even though we come across this notion of care in our daily lives, the ontological significance of the manifestation of care is through *Dasein*. the Being of *Dasein* is a given, and its existential meaning

is care. This is in tandem with his saying that "*Dasein*, when understood ontologically, is care," because the notion of "Being-in-the-world" is care or concern because it is a characteristic of Being. Heidegger also asserts the ontological relation between Being-in-the-world (care), Being-with (solitude), and Being-one's-self. This ontological relationship is inherent and inseparable in *Dasein*. Heidegger's notion of care is influenced by Aristotle's use of the term "reach out for," which he translates as care (Heidegger et al., 1962).

Heidegger defines care as the ontological structural concept that shows the relationship between Being and *Dasein*. It is how *Dasein* looks out into the world and manifests its existence. Care can be understood as the fundamental mode of being for *Dasein*, where it is always already engaged with the world and concerned with its existence. For example, when we experience concern for something or someone and are attentive and responsive to the needs and possibilities of the world, we are manifesting care. This can be seen in everyday actions such as taking care of loved ones, being concerned about our well-being, or being attentive to the environment around us. Hence, care entails the ontological responsibility of humans to the world; this responsibility is executed by *Dasein* reaching out to Being.

Dasein seeks what is distant to bring it near to himself, and care is a way of reaching out and bringing to nearness Being. For Heidegger, this reaching out is more potent when we are at rest when he says that "care subsides into circumspection which has been set free" and this level of circumspection is not potent in the "world of work"(Heidegger et al., 1962). At rest, we are free from concerns, and "circumspection" is set free. However, this reaching out is not merely to grasp something as to understand it but, at rest, manifests the possibility of *Dasein* abandoning or surrendering itself to the world. The phenomenon of care articulates the fundamental question of the meaning of Being, according to Heidegger, because *Dasein's* Being reveals itself through care. Care must be properly articulated and cannot be derived from concepts like will, wish, addiction, and urge since these concepts are based on care.

While care may share similarities with concepts like will, wish, addiction, and urge, it is fundamentally different from them. Care is not simply a matter of

wanting, desiring, or being driven by impulses. Unlike will, which is often associated with conscious decision-making and deliberate action, care is a more primordial and fundamental mode of being for *Dasein*. It is not something that can be reduced to a specific intention or desire but rather encompasses the entire mode of *Dasein's* existence. Similarly, care differs from addiction or urge, which are often associated with compulsive behaviours or actions driven by external forces. Care, on the other hand, is an inherent and inseparable aspect of *Dasein's* being, always already engaged with and concerned about its existence and the world it inhabits. This culmination of Heidegger's analysis is demonstrated when *Dasein* expresses itself to itself, and then it interprets itself as care pre-ontologically (Heidegger et al., 1962).

For Heidegger, theory and practice are both possibilities of *Dasein* and cannot be put asunder through this dichotomy. Care is "a primordial structural totality," and the factual attitude and situation of *Dasein* are a priori. The substance of man is existence, as care belongs both to the notion of Being-in-the-world and within-the-world. Care is a mode of articulating the truth of existence and also a mode of authentic disclosedness. Heidegger believes that by articulating the phenomenon of care, we have shown the ontological structure of *Dasein* as Being and its ontological relation to itself and the world. Through this concept, we arrive at *Dasein's* primordial state of Being and disclose the ontological state of *Dasein's* existence. Hence, care reveals the entire structure of Being-in-the-world and the phenomenon of existence. Care is the authentic expression of *Dasein's* fundamental Being, and its essential true self (Heidegger et al., 1962).

In Heidegger's philosophy, care is closely linked to Being-in-the-world and Being-with. Being-in-the-world refers to the inherent interconnectedness of *Dasein* with the world, where *Dasein* exists as a being that is always already engaged with and embedded in the world. Care is the ontological manifestation of this Being-in-the-world, as it is through care that *Dasein* is attentive and responsive to the world. Being-with, on the other hand, refers to the social dimension of *Dasein's* existence, where *Dasein* exists relative to others and is fundamentally shaped by these relationships. Care is also intimately connected to Being-with, as *Dasein's* care is not only directed towards the world but also toward others. This

interconnectedness between care, Being-in-the-world, and Being-with demonstrates the holistic nature of *Dasein's* existence.

Thus, Heidegger's analysis elucidates the notion of ontological responsibility to others and the world. Care is not just a solitary act but rather a fundamental aspect of our existence that is inseparable from our relationships with others and the world. It is through our care for others and the world that we fulfil our ontological responsibility to be attentive and responsive to the needs and concerns of those around us. This understanding of care as interconnected with Being-in-the-world and Being-with highlights the importance of considering the impact of our actions on others and the world as we navigate our existence. This notion of interconnectedness is particularly relevant to our relationship with nature. When we recognise that our care extends beyond human relationships and encompasses the natural world, we realise that our actions have a profound impact on the environment. By acknowledging this interconnectedness, we can strive to cultivate a more sustainable and harmonious relationship with nature, ensuring the well-being of both present and future generations.

Implications for Environmental Sustainability

The implications of Heidegger's notion of *dwelling* on environmental sustainability are significant, as it challenges traditional views of human existence and relationships with nature. Heidegger's ontology provides a nuanced view of the consequences of humans' estrangement from nature. Firstly, Heidegger's articulation of the notion of *dwelling* buttresses the idea of ontological oneness. This challenges the prevailing dualistic perspective that separates humans from nature and encourages a more holistic understanding of our interconnectedness with nature. Dwelling, according to Heidegger, "is how mortals are on the earth"(Heidegger 2001). This implies that humans are not separate entities inhabiting the earth but rather integral parts of the natural world. For him, there is no distinction between being a human being and *dwelling*; they are one and the same.

Heidegger further opines that the fundamental character of *dwelling* is "to spare" and "to preserve"(Heidegger 2001). This suggests that humans have a responsibility to care for and protect the environment in which they dwell,

recognising their interconnectedness with nature. Hence, our ontological responsibility is "to cherish and protect, to preserve and care for, specifically to till the soil, to cultivate the vine." Heidegger's ontological oneness is in tandem with ecological theory and environmental sustainability. Ecological theory emphasises the interconnectedness of all living entities and the importance of preserving ecosystems for future generations. It also emphasises our responsibility to care for the environment, primarily because of its inherent value.

The idea of environmental sustainability is implied in Heidegger's notion of *dwelling*. Environmental sustainability entails the management of natural resources over the long term. It involves using resources in a way that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. By understanding and embracing Heidegger's concept of *dwelling*, we can strive towards a more sustainable and harmonious relationship with the natural world. A befitting conclusion to Heidegger's perspective on his conception of care. Care for Heidegger is our ontological responsibility to nature, and this is established when we cherish, protect, cultivate, and preserve nature. This notion of responsibility to nature is not particular to Heidegger, Arne Naess, deep ecology also encourages a change in our attitude towards nature and the promotion of an environmental approach based on the recognition of the inherent value in nature as a whole (Naess 2017).

In contrast to deep ecology, Heidegger advocates for a more existential approach to our relationship with nature, emphasising the interconnectedness and interdependence of all beings. His approach could be considered somewhat anthropocentric because it places a strong emphasis on human existence and experience within the natural world. However, Heidegger also stresses the importance of recognising the intrinsic value of nature and the need for humans to live in harmony with it by letting nature be. Deep ecology, on the other hand, focuses on the idea that all living beings have equal value and deserve respect and consideration. This perspective encourages a more holistic view of nature, emphasising the interconnectedness of all species and the importance of environmental sustainability.

Summary

Heidegger's notion of *dwelling* emphasises the importance of recognising our interconnectedness with the environment and the need to care for it as a fundamental aspect of our existence. By embodying this perspective, we can work towards creating a more sustainable future for both ourselves and future generations. In *Poetry, Language, Thought*, Heidegger delves into the concept of *dwelling*, emphasising its relationship with nature. He argues that *dwelling* is a fundamental aspect of our nature as mortals on earth, and both terms are ontologically inseparable. He defines *dwelling* as cherishing, protecting, preserving, and caring for, specifically tilling the soil and cultivating the vine. He distinguishes between building as cultivating and building as constructing, which involve stewardship towards nature and the physical creation of structures that shape the human-made landscape. Both cultivation and construction are essential aspects of building, reflecting our desire to shape and experience the world. Heidegger goes further to stating the human-nature connection through his postulation of the fourfold.

Heidegger's concept of the fourfold is a philosophical concept that emphasises the interconnectedness and interdependence of mortals, divinities, earth, and sky within the primal notion of *dwelling*. It emphasises the importance of preserving this balance to maintain freedom and allow nature to exist in its natural state. Recognising and respecting this fourfold allows individuals to cultivate a deeper connection to nature and live more authentically. Heidegger's concept of the fourfold emphasises the importance of understanding the interconnectedness of all beings and the environment. By examining the jug as a container, Heidegger demonstrates the fundamental feature of the jug's ability to hold and retain its contents, highlighting the interconnectedness of being and the importance of preserving this balance.

In his work, *Being and Time*, Heidegger emphasises the importance of care as a fundamental structure of human existence. Care is not just a feeling or emotion but a mode of being-in-the-world that shapes our understanding of ourselves, others, and the world around us. He uses the term "sorge" to describe the relationship between humans and Being, highlighting the ontological significance of care through *Dasein* (Heidegger 2010). Care is an inherent and inseparable

aspect of *Dasein's* being, always engaging with and concerned about its existence and the world it inhabits. Heidegger believes that theory and practice are both possibilities of *Dasein* and cannot be put asunder through this dichotomy. Care is closely linked to Being-in-the-world and Being-with, referring to the inherent interconnectedness of *Dasein* with the world and the social dimension of its existence. Recognising this interconnectedness can help cultivate a more sustainable and harmonious relationship with nature, ensuring the well-being of present and future generations.

In summary, Heidegger emphasises the importance of understanding *Dasein's* existence as intertwined with the world around it, leading to a more holistic approach to being. By recognising this interconnectedness, we can strive towards a more ethical relationship with nature, promoting a healthier environment for all beings and future generations. This perspective challenges us to consider our attitude, our impact on the environment, and the consequences of our actions. Heidegger's philosophy encourages us to reflect on our place in the world and strive towards a more sustainable and ethical way of being.

Conclusion

In conclusion, embracing Heidegger's notion of *dwelling* can lead to a deeper appreciation for our interconnectedness with the world and inspire us to make more conscious choices that benefit not only ourselves but also the environment. This can contribute to creating a more harmonious and sustainable world for all living beings. By changing our attitude towards nature and adopting a more intentional approach to all aspects of our existence, we can work towards building a better future for generations to come. This change in attitude can lead to a more balanced and respectful relationship with the environment, fostering a sense of responsibility for the well-being of the planet by adopting Heidegger's notion of care. By practising care and mindfulness, we can begin to cultivate a deeper connection with the natural world around us. This can lead to a more harmonious coexistence between humanity and the environment, ensuring a healthier planet for both present and future generations.

Reference

- Goodland, R. (1995). The concept of environmental sustainability. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 1–24.
- Heidegger, M. (2001). *Poetry, Language, Thought (Perennial Classics)*. Cidade: HarperCollins Publishers.
- Heidegger, M. (2010). *Being and Time: A Revised Edition of the Stambaugh Translation*. SUNY Press.
- Heidegger, M., Macquarrie, J., & Robinson, E. (1962). *Being and time*.
- Leopold, A. (1970). *A sand county Almanac*. 1949. *New York: Ballantine*.
- Morelli, J. (2011). Environmental sustainability: A definition for environmental professionals. *Journal of Environmental Sustainability*, 1(1), 2.
- Naess, A. (2017). The shallow and the deep, long-range ecology movement. A summary. In *The Ethics of the Environment* (pp. 115–120). Routledge.
- Norton, B. G. (2005). *Sustainability: A philosophy of adaptive ecosystem management*. University of Chicago Press.
- Our common future*. (1987). Oxford University Press.
- Scoones, I. (2007). Sustainability. *Development in Practice*, 17(4–5), 589–596.
- Zaner, R. M., & Ihde, D. (Eds.). (1973). *Phenomenology and Existentialism*. Capricorn Books.